

ON MONITORING OF RESERVE LANDS IN THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Mamajonova Nodira Alisher qizi

senior teacher, department of applied mathematics and informatics

Andijan institute of construction economics

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INTRODUCTION

In the current market economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is important to organize land monitoring in order to increase the level of land use and increase the volume of land production. Land monitoring, which is being introduced in the country today, is aimed at assessing the current state of the land fund, its assessment, timely detection of changes in quality and quantity, elimination of possible negative consequences of land use includes a system of observations. Land monitoring consists of a system for monitoring the condition and quality of the land fund in order to identify changes in the composition of the land in a timely manner, assess the land, prevent and eliminate the consequences of negative processes.

METHODS

ABSTRACT

This article describes the procedures for monitoring land reserves.

Land monitoring is one of the main components of environmental monitoring and is the basis of other environmental monitoring. Land monitoring is carried out on the basis of the state land cadastre, land use, land management, state control over the purpose and rational use of land resources, information support of land protection bodies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The condition of lands is assessed by analyzing a number of consistent observations (periodic, seasonal, daily) on the direction and intensity of changes, comparing the obtained indicators with the norms of land quality. Land use indicators are expressed in both absolute and relative terms (units of measurement) for a given period or date. Based on the results of land assessment, operational data, information, forecasts and recommendations are compiled, accompanied by thematic maps,

cartograms, tables and diagrams describing the dynamics of changes, especially their direction and intensity. All lands of the republic, regardless of their legal regime, purpose and nature of use, are the object of land monitoring. Republican, regional and

local monitoring of lands is carried out according to regional coverage. Republican monitoring covers the entire territory of the Republic. Local monitoring covers individual plots of land and landscape-ecological complexes.

Land monitoring is a single method developed and approved by the State Committee for Land Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the participation of interested ministries, state committees and agencies, which conducts rapid and regular monitoring of land conditions, conducts research, inspections or mapping is mandatory for all businesses and organizations. The basic data obtained from direct observation of the state of arable lands, plots, landscape ecological complexes are summarized by districts,

cities, fortresses, regions, the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Republic of Uzbekistan in general, as well as by individual natural complexes. Coordination of the activities of ministries and departments, generalization of land monitoring data is carried out by the State Committee for Land Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main tasks of land monitoring in the Republic of Uzbekistan are: - organization and implementation of a system of monitoring the timely detection of changes in the state

of the land fund, their assessment, forecasting of negative processes and the development of recommendations for their prevention and elimination; - providing information on state control over the maintenance of state land cadastre, land use, land management, targeted and rational use of land resources, land

protection and other functions of state management of land resources. Given the fact that land monitoring is part of a system of continuous state measures, we consider it expedient to carry out organizational management in the first stage. This includes the following tasks:

The purpose and objectives of land monitoring are based on the following principles:

1. The principle of comparison and correlation of different data. It is based on the use of uniform classifiers, formats, data of the normative and technical base, coordinates and a single state system of height; 2. The principle of unity, which implies the compatibility of monitoring, the unity of technologies and methods; 3. The

principle of accuracy and reliability, which characterizes the degree to which the use and condition of the land fund really corresponds to the data of land monitoring; 4. The principle of completeness of information - the information must be complete and sufficient to solve specific problems; 5. The principle of continuous land monitoring. In the process of restructuring land relations, changes in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics

of the country's land fund, changes in some of its categories, increasing anthropogenic burden on land resources, various changes in the distribution and composition of land resources. Therefore, it is important to ensure the continuity of land monitoring through periodic or regular updates. Remote sensing of the land fund is carried out using 2 main groups of equipment: Video and official information (aerial photography equipment, multi-zone scanning equipment, radar, TV channels, etc.); Instruments of track groups (spectrometers, SVCH and IR - radiometers, etc.). It is carried out at ground observation landfills, reference sites, automated stationary data collection points for the preparation of agro-space information, and when this information is not available by remote sensing, to obtain information on the status of the land fund. The following equipment can be included in the set of ground monitoring equipment: Ground moving stations; Instruments equipped for high-speed passage of vehicles on the

highway and chemical analysis of changes in soil moisture, as well as the transmission of computers and telemetry; A set of hardware that provides the receiving device.

CONCLUSION

Preliminary data of local monitoring are collected, which describe the appearance of land and water property in administrative districts, cities, plots, individual fields, land use and land tenure, the state of the entire land fund. In the autonomous republics and regions of the Republic, the data containing all the information on the districts, cities, as well as some objects of ecological and regional characterization are formed. The formed database and bank of land monitoring can use: In short, it is more convenient to monitor lands using modern and effective technologies. In this case, it is advisable to monitor the state of the earth using aerospace images. The use of satellite imagery to identify unused areas allows for the simultaneous acquisition of information over a very large area.

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